

A study to assess the knowledge on infection control measure among staff nurses Operation theatre at Dr Vitthalrao Vikhe Patil Rural Hospital, Loni..

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Abstract

Background: Infection control in the operation theatre (OT) is critical for patient safety. The effectiveness of these measures is largely dependent on the knowledge and practice of the nursing staff. Despite established protocols, lapses in infection control can lead to adverse outcomes, making it imperative to assess and enhance the knowledge of staff nurses in this environment.

The aim of your study, as outlined in the document, is to evaluate the knowledge and practices of infection control among staff nurses in the operation theatre (OT) at Dr. Vitthalrao Vikhe Patil Pravara Rural Hospital, Loni. This evaluation seeks to identify gaps that could be addressed to enhance patient safety and improve infection prevention measures.

Methodology: A descriptive study was conducted among staff nurses working in the OT of Dr. Vitthalrao Vikhe Patil Pravara Rural Hospital. A structured questionnaire was used to assess knowledge. Data were analyzed using appropriate statistical methods to determine the correlation between knowledge and practice.

Results: The findings indicate a varying degree of knowledge among the staff nurses. While some nurses demonstrated high levels of both knowledge and practice, others exhibited significant gaps, particularly in the consistent application of infection control measures.

Conclusion: In conclusion, while staff nurses at Dr. Vitthalrao Vikhe Patil Pravara Rural Hospital demonstrate a fair understanding of infection control measures, there are critical areas needing improvement, particularly in the consistent application of these measures in the operation theatre. Enhancing the knowledge and practices of infection control through targeted interventions will be crucial in reducing the risk of HAIs and improving patient outcomes.

- **Keywords :-** Assess, Infection Control, Knowledge, Staff Nurses, Operating Theater (OT), Healthcare-Associated Infections (HAIs), Surgical Site Infections (SSIs)

Introduction :-

Infection was recognized as a major preventable cause of mortality and morbidity. Apart from the emphasis on general measures of asepsis in the care of patient, infection control measures also must be followed in the Operation theatre. Infection refers to invasion and multiplication of microorganisms in body tissues, especially that causing local cellular injury due to competitive metabolism, toxins, intracellular replication or antigen – antibody response.

Modern healthcare relies heavily on infection control, especially in high-risk settings like operating rooms where the danger of healthcare-associated infections (HAIs) is greatly increased. Operating rooms are sterile settings used for performing surgical procedures, many of which include invasive methods that put the patient's body at risk of infection. In order to avoid post-operative infections, which can have serious repercussions such as increased morbidity, mortality, and longer hospital stays, it is imperative that sterility be maintained in these settings. Staff nurses are among the many medical specialists that provide surgical treatment, and they are essential to the execution and enforcement of infection control protocols. They are responsible for setting up the operating room, sterilizing the instruments, helping with the surgery, and making sure the surgical team rigorously adheres to all infection control measures.

Background of the study

Infection control is not just about following protocols; it involves a deep understanding of the principles behind these practices and the ability to apply them consistently in a clinical setting. For staff nurses in the OT, this means being well-versed in the latest guidelines, understanding the risks associated with different surgical procedures, and

being able to identify potential breaches in aseptic technique. The knowledge and attitudes of staff nurses towards infection control can significantly influence their practices, and consequently, the safety of the surgical environment. Therefore, assessing the knowledge base of these nurses is a crucial step in ensuring that infection control measures are being implemented effectively.

Historically, infection control has evolved significantly, with early practices dating back to the late 19th century when the germ theory of disease was first recognized by pioneers like Louis Pasteur and Joseph Lister. Since then, the principles of asepsis and antisepsis have become foundational to modern surgical practices. However, despite advances in medical science and the development of sophisticated sterilization techniques, challenges in infection control persist, particularly in resource-limited settings such as rural hospitals. The operation theatre, by its very nature, demands meticulous adherence to protocols to ensure that the sterile environment is maintained, reducing the risk of HAIs. Staff nurses, who are integral members of the surgical team, play a vital role in implementing these protocols, from preparing the patient and environment to handling instruments and ensuring compliance with hand hygiene practices.

Material and Methods :-

Study area and population :- The population for this study consists of all staff nurses currently working in the operation theatre at Dr. Vitthalrao Vikhe Patil Pravara Rural Hospital, Loni Bk.’’

Research Design : Non Experimental Descriptive Research design

Inclusion criteria :-

Nursing staff who is:

- a) Staff of OT.
- b) Willing to participate in the study.
- c) Available during time of data collection.

Exclusive criteria:

Nursing staff who:

- A. Is not willing to participate.
- B. Feels uncomfortable during time of data collection.

- C. Critically ill patients who were not sufficiently alert to be able to respond to questions.

Sample size and Sampling technique: -

A sample size of 50 is proposed for this study. This number is selected based on the availability and willingness of the staff nurses to participate. A sample of this size is considered adequate for a descriptive cross-sectional study to provide meaningful insights into the knowledge and practices related to infection control. Non probability purposive sampling technique is used for present study.

Data Collection & Analysis:-

The data collection procedure for assessing the knowledge on infection control measures among staff nurses in the operation theatre at Dr. Vitthalrao Vikhe Patil Pravara Rural Hospital involves a structured, phased approach to ensure the reliability and validity of the data collected. All the participants provided informed consent and confidentiality was maintained.

Analysis:

- 1. Descriptive Statistics:** Frequency , percentage ,mean , Standard deviation was used to assess the knowledge and practice regarding infection control among staff nurses working in operation theatre
- 2. Inferential statistics :**

Chi-Square Tests:

The relationship between categorical variables such as educational background, previous training in infection control, and levels of knowledge will be assessed using chi-square tests.

This analysis will help identify whether there is a significant association between these demographic variables and the knowledge levels of the staff nurses.

Results: -

Findings of Socio-demographic variables :-

Findings related to Socio-demographic data of preoperative orthopaedic patient

Majority of the subjects were (62%) in the age group of 31-40 years, Majority of the subjects (62 %) were male „Majority of the subjects (78 %) hold diploma education and lower

qualification , Highest percentage (64%) had 5-10 years of working experience ,Majority of the respondents (74%) had attended formal training of infection control before.

Knowledge Regarding Infection control among Staff nurses

Table No - 01

Frequency and percentage distribution of Knowledge Regarding Infection control among Staff nurses

SN	Level of Knowledge	Range of score	Frequency	Percentage
1	Poor Knowledge	0-5	14	28%
2	Average Knowledge	6-10	16	32%
3	Good Knowledge	11-15	30	60%

Area wise distribution of mean , SD on Assessment of Knowledge Regarding Infection control among Staff nurses, shows that majority 60% of the Staff nurses had Good Knowledge, 32% had Average knowledge and 28% Had Poor knowledge.

Table No - 02

Association between level of Knowledge Regarding Infection control among Staff nurses with demographic variables

n = 50

SN	Variables	X ²	Level of significance
1	Age	4.66	Significant
2	Gender	4.21	Significant
3	Educational qualification	2.13	Non Significant
4	Working experience	2.76	Non Significant
5	Did you received formal training of infection control before	4.65	Significant

Df =49 , table – 3.84 , $p \leq 0.05$

Chi square values were calculated to find out the association between level of Knowledge Regarding Infection control among Staff nurses with demographic variable, the findings revealed that there was significant association between level of knowledge among Staff nurses with demographic variable like Age ,Gender and Did you received formal training of infection control before .hence the stated null hypothesis (HO2)Was rejected as there was significant association between level of Knowledge Regarding Infection control among Staff nurses with demographic variable.

Discussion :-

Findings are discussed under the following heading:

- Findings related to level knowledge on Infection control among Staff nurses.
- Findings related to association between Findings related to level of knowledge on Infection control among Staff nurses with their demographic variable

A. Findings related to level of knowledge on Infection control among Staff nurses

Assessment of Knowledge Regarding Infection control among Staff nurses, shows that majority 60% of the Staff nurses had Good Knowledge, 32% had Average knowledge and 28% Had Poor knowledge.

B. Findings related to association between Findings related to level of knowledge on Infection control among Staff nurses with their demographic variable

Chi square values were calculated to find out the association between level of Knowledge Regarding Infection control among Staff nurses with demographic variable, the findings revealed that there was significant association between level of knowledge among Staff nurses with demographic variable like Age ,Gender and Did you received formal training of infection control before .hence the stated null hypothesis (HO2)Was rejected as there was significant association between level of Knowledge Regarding Infection control among Staff nurses with demographic variable.

Limitations: -

This study was limited only to the 50 staff nurses working in operation theatre .The study did not use any control group.

Conclusion: -

The findings of the present study indicated regarding level of Knowledge Regarding Infection control among Staff nurses, shows that majority of staff nurses had good knowledge regarding infection control .

Recommendations:-

Based on the study finding the following recommendations have made for the further study

- Similar study may be replicated on large samples for wider generalization.
- Similar study can be conducted in community.
- Similar study can be conducted through experimental research approach
- Manuals, information booklets and self instruction module may be developed in mental health area for general public.

Acknowledgments: -

The authors of this study would like to acknowledge to all the participants.

Conflict of Interest: - None to declare

Human subjects: -

Consent was obtained by all participants in this study. Issued ethical approval from Institutional Ethics Committee MUHS/PG/E-6/153345/1968/2022.

Author's Contribution: -

All authors contributed in conceptualization of study, analysis.

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